

DIABETES AND TECHNOLOGY: A REVIEW OF INNOVATIONS IN MONITORING AND TREATMENT

NEELAM YADAV¹, PALLAVI BADHAN³, MANISHA JADAV^{2*}

¹Department of Quality Assurance, School of Pharmacy, Parul University, P.O. Limda, Ta. Waghodia – 391760, Gujarat, India

²Department of Quality Assurance, School of Pharmacy, Parul University, P.O. Limda, Ta. Waghodia – 391760, Gujarat, India

^{3*}Department of Quality Assurance, School of Pharmacy, Parul University, P.O. Limda, Ta. Waghodia – 391760, Gujarat, India

*Correspondence:

Mrs. Manisha Jadav

Department of Quality Assurance
School of Pharmacy, Parul University
Gujarat-390025, India

ABSTRACT

Diabetes is a prevalent chronic condition that impacts approximately 285 million adults globally. The increasing occurrence of diabetes, metabolic syndrome and the resulting vascular diseases represents a significant public health challenge in developed nations. The elevated prevalence of diabetes mellitus (DM), coupled with suboptimal health outcomes and rising treatment and care expenses, underscores the necessity to emphasize disease prevention, early identification, and enhanced disease management. There is substantial potential for the creation of a new wave of therapeutics aimed at providing more effective control over diabetes, its coexisting conditions, and associated complications. This article provides an overview of current technologies, drugs, treatment and pharmacological methods for addressing diabetes mellitus while concentrating on emerging or already developed innovative treatments for diabetes mellitus.

Keywords: Diabetes mellitus, diagnosis, treatment, technology

INTRODUCTION

“Diabetes is a chronic, metabolic disease characterized by elevated levels of blood glucose (or blood sugar), which leads over time to serious damage to the heart, blood vessels, eyes, kidneys and nerves.”^[1]

Diabetes is a condition that disrupts the metabolism of carbohydrates, proteins and fats. Diabetes mellitus (DM) stands as the topmost widespread endocrine disorders, impacting more than 100 million people worldwide. It results from an insufficient or inefficient production of insulin by the pancreas, causing fluctuations in blood glucose levels, which can either rise or fall. This ailment is recognized for its capacity to harm various physiological systems, notably affecting blood vessels, heart, nerves, eyes, and kidneys.^[2,3]

Fig.1: Normal blood glucose vs. High blood glucose

Diabetes mellitus (DM) is frequently colloquially referred to as "sugar." According to the “International Diabetes Federation” (IDF), estimated total count of individuals with diabetes in India is approximately 40.9 million, and this number is projected to increase to 69.9 million by the year 2025.^[4,5]

The management of diabetes mellitus aims to achieve four primary goals: (1) Alleviating symptoms, (2) Sustaining proper nutritional balance, (3) Safeguarding the pancreas's ability to produce insulin, and (4) Mitigating or averting complications.^[6,7]

TYPES OF DIABETES MELLITUS

Diabetes mellitus can be categorized into different types:^[8]

- **Type I diabetes** (Insulin-dependent) is the outcome of the immune-mediated destruction of beta cells, causing a deficiency of insulin.
- **Idiopathic diabetes** is a subtype of Type 1 diabetes with no identifiable causes, and it often has a strong genetic component.
- **Type II diabetes**, (Non-Insulin dependent diabetes), is distinguished by the presence of both an insulin secretory dysfunction and insulin resistance.
- **Gestational diabetes** mellitus pertains to any form of glucose intolerance identified or diagnosed for the first time during pregnancy.

Additional forms of diabetes^[9]

- **LADA** (Latent Autoimmune Diabetes of Adults) is an autoimmune diabetes variant characterized by its onset in adulthood, the presence of diabetes-related autoantibodies, and a lack of immediate insulin therapy need following diagnosis.
- **Maturity-onset diabetes of the young (MODY)** is a type of diabetes that doesn't depend on insulin and is typically identified during early adulthood. MODY is commonly inherited in an autosomal dominant manner.
- **Neonatal diabetes** is a unique diabetes variant that typically emerges before the age of six months. It distinguishes itself from the more prevalent type 1 diabetes since it does not involve an autoimmune response, where the body targets and destroys its insulin-producing cells.

DIAGNOSIS

“The American Diabetes Association” (ADA) recommends the utilization of fasting glucose concentration as a standard method for diabetes screening. However, healthcare professionals may also employ postprandial tests like blood sugar tests, random blood sugar tests, and glucose tolerance tests to determine blood sugar levels.^[10]

- In order to diagnose diabetes, a minimum of one of the following criteria must be satisfied:
- “Symptoms of diabetes (polyurea, polydipsia, unexplained weight loss, etc) as well as casual plasma glucose concentration = 11.1 mmol/L (200 mg/dL).”
- “Fasting plasma glucose = its normal range is 70-110 mg/dL with no caloric intake for at least 8 hour.”

Tests used in the diagnosis of diabetes mellitus:

There are three blood tests used for diagnosing prediabetes and diabetes:^[11,12]

1. Casual plasma (blood) glucose/random plasma test
2. Fasting plasma glucose (FPG)
3. Oral glucose Tolerance test

INNOVATIONS IN TREATMENT AND MANAGEMENT OF DIABETES^[13,14]

1. Artificial pancreas and advanced closed-loop systems

There has been a significant amount of enthusiasm and research in islet transplantation. However, as of the present moment, sustained independence can reliably be achieved in the long term through the transplantation of an entire pancreas organ from exogenous insulin and the normalization of HbA1C levels.^[15]

The advantages of pancreas transplantation are evident, including:^[16]

- Overall well-being and quality of life.
- Preventing the recurrence of diabetic nephropathy.
- Independence from external insulin dependence, leading to euglycemia and normalized HbA1C levels.

Fig.2: Artificial Pancreas treatment for diabetes

The artificial pancreas device (APD) operates as a closed-loop control system designed to regulate blood glucose levels in people with diabetes.

This closed-loop APD consists of three primary components:

- glucose sensor
- an insulin infusion device
- control algorithm

APD can be categorized based on its configuration. There are single-hormone APDs, which exclusively administer insulin, and dual-hormone APDs, which provide both insulin and glucagon.^[17]

A fully automated closed-loop APD is defined as an externally worn medical device system with 3 primary functions:

- (1) Delivering insulin via an insulin infusion pump
- (2) Tracking glucose levels through a Continuous Glucose Monitor (CGM)
- (3) Managing these functions using a digital controller.^[18]

2. Islet cell transplantation

The keen interest in islet transplantation in humans emerged in 2000 with the introduction of the “Edmonton protocol”. Nonetheless, this protocol faces several substantial challenges, including the inadequate supply of islets due to the limited number of available cadaveric pancreas donors, the complexities of ongoing immune rejection, and the risk of autoimmunity recurrence. This is because many conventional immunosuppressive regimens can be detrimental to islets.^[19]

Fig.3: Islet cell transplant

A continuous and progressive decline in insulin production from transplanted islets among diabetic recipients has been consistently noted over time. This observation is backed by reports indicating that 30-40% of individuals receiving islet transplants might encounter a resurgence of autoimmune diabetes and revert to requiring insulin within one to two years post-transplantation.

Another constraining element is the process of islet revascularization, which seems to have a notable impact on establishing the long-term viability and optimal functionality of the transplanted islet cluster. The swift establishment of a sufficient microvascular system in freshly transplanted islets is crucial for the endurance and effectiveness of islet grafts.^[20]

Ultimately, these endeavors aim to enhance the outcomes of islet transplantation by reducing the donor-to-recipient ratio, thereby increasing the success rate of islet transplantation.^[21]

3. Stem cells

Stem cells serve as an alternative reservoir of transplantable β -cells. Stem cells possess the unique ability to replicate while staying undifferentiated and preserving the potential to transform into specialized cell types when provided with the right conditions. The origins of these stem cells for producing β -cells were first revealed in various investigations involving both adult and fetal pancreas. The primary sources of stem cells for this aim include embryonic stem cells and the more recent induced pluripotent stem cells. The latter are created from mature adult cells through methods involving the introduction of transcription factor DNA or recombinant transcription factor proteins.^[22,23,24]

Fig. 4: Stem cells therapy

4. Advanced insulin analogues

The development of insulin analogs through structural-based protein design is a notable achievement. Understanding the arrangements of insulin hexamers, formed by a trimer of dimers coordinated by zinc and functioning as a storage form for the active insulin monomer, has played a crucial role. Early investigations primarily concentrated on disrupting subunit interfaces. By intentionally destabilizing these interfaces, the disassembly process that promotes rapid absorption into capillaries was facilitated, leading to the creation of fast-acting insulin analogs.^[25]

There are ongoing investigations into modified approaches to further enhance the pharmacokinetic properties of these products.

Insulins that have the quickest onset of action are commonly known as rapid-acting insulins.^{[26][27]}

These rapid-acting insulins encompass:

- Aspart
- Glulisine
- Lyspro

Rapid-acting insulin analogs swiftly get into the bloodstream, necessitating administration in a span of 5 to 10 minutes following a meal. They usually exhibit a peak action period of 60-120 minutes and their impact diminishes entirely after approximately four hours.

In certain instances, higher doses may lead to a slightly extended duration but generally do not exceed five or six hours.

Long-acting injected insulin analogs

Insulins with the most extended duration of action are categorized as long-acting insulins. They sustain relatively consistent insulin levels that remain at a plateau for extended durations post-injection. On occasion, these insulins are referred to as "peakless" insulins. Typically, they begin to take effect within 60-90 minutes, reach their peak effectiveness in about 5 hours, and then gradually decrease over the subsequent 12-24 hours.

They include:

1. Insulin detemir (Levemir®):
 - Typically administered with two injections per day.
2. Insulin glargine (Lantus®):

Typically, long-acting insulins are administered once daily, although in certain situations, they may be given twice daily as required.

Extended-release insulin analogs are well-suited for providing uninterrupted background or basal insulin replacement. Administering insulin detemir and glargine at consistent daily intervals is vital to uphold the most stable and foreseeable basal insulin levels within the body.

5. Continuous glucose monitoring system

Fig.5: Continuous Glucose Monitoring of diabetes

A continuous glucose monitor (CGM) is a compact medical device that continually tracks your glucose levels in nearly real-time (typically with a 5-minute interval between readings).^{[28][29]}

To utilize a CGM, a small sensor is placed on the abdomen or arm using a minute plastic tube called a cannula that penetrates the outermost layer of the skin. An adhesive patch secures the sensor in position, enabling it for continuous monitoring of glucose levels in the interstitial fluid (the fluid surrounding cells in the body) around the clock. Typically, these sensors need to be replaced every 7 to 14 days.

A compact and reusable transmitter, linked to the sensor, facilitates the wireless transmission of real-time readings to a monitoring device, which displays the blood glucose data. Certain systems include a designated monitor, while others now provide the information through a smartphone app, eliminating the need to carry an additional device.^[30]

6. Gene based therapies

Gene therapy is the practice of introducing or altering genetic material within cells as a therapeutic method for managing illnesses. Its objective is to rectify malfunctioning genes that contribute to the development of diseases, ultimately either preventing disease initiation or arresting its advancement.^[31]

A rising and auspicious substitute for conventional diabetes treatments is gene-based therapy. Driven by cutting-edge biotechnologies and the triumphant culmination of the Human Genome Project, gene therapy is often celebrated as one of the most auspicious technologies of the 21st century. While certain challenges still require resolution, the trade-off between risks and benefits ratio of gene therapy in the context of diabetes appears to outshine all other presently employed treatment methods.^[32]

Fig.6: Gene based therapy

Gene therapy aims to convey genetic material with therapeutic value. This procedure depends on three crucial elements: (a) an in-depth comprehension of the disease's development, (b) the accurate genetic codes to aim for, and (c) consistent delivery mechanisms that furnish the pertinent tissues with the required level and duration of genetic activity to accomplish the intended therapeutic result.

7. Incretin based therapies and GLP-1 agonists^{[33][34][35]}

Incretin-derived treatments, specifically glucagon-like peptide-1 receptor agonists (GLP-1 RAs), have shown their capability to provide cardiovascular benefits to individuals diagnosed with type 2 diabetes. Nonetheless, variations in its usage rooted in socioeconomic aspects may restrict the overall benefits these drugs can provide to the broader population. Real-world data reveals that the utilization of GLP-1 RAs is less common among patients living in socioeconomically challenged regions, individuals with lower income and education levels, or those from racial/ethnic minority backgrounds. Interestingly, these groups often bear a higher burden of type 2 diabetes and cardiovascular disease. Multiple factors contribute to these discrepancies, including insufficient Healthcare policy, constrained access to incretin-based treatments, monetary limitations, inadequate health awareness, and barriers in the doctor-patient relationship. An essential first step in addressing this issue is advocating for a decrease in the cost of GLP-1 RAs. This would make them more affordable for individuals from lower socioeconomic backgrounds and enhance their cost-effectiveness from a societal standpoint.

8. Oral semaglutide

Oral semaglutide marks a notable achievement as the inaugural oral product in the category of glucagon-like peptide 1 (GLP-1) receptor agonists to gain approval from the U.S. Food and Drug Administration (FDA) for managing type 2 diabetes. The category of is extensively employed and recommended for the treatment of type 2 diabetes.

“The American Diabetes Association's Standards of Medical Care in Diabetes—2019 recommend GLP-1 receptor agonists with proven cardiovascular advantages as one of the top two choices for supplementary therapy in individuals with type 2 diabetes and pre-existing atherosclerotic cardiovascular disease, after metformin and lifestyle modifications.”

Medications within this category are also commonly suggested as supplementary treatment following metformin in cases where patients fail to reach their personalized glycemic targets, particularly when there is a significant need to reduce the risk of hypoglycemia or encourage weight loss.

Traditionally, administration of GLP-1 receptor agonists necessitates self-injection via subcutaneous means. The introduction of oral semaglutide offers a novel preference within this category, providing advantages for patients who may have difficulty or reservations about self-administering injectable medications.^[36]

FDA approval for the utilization of oral semaglutide was granted in September 2019. It is authorized as a supplement to diet and physical activity to enhance glycemic management in adults diagnosed with type 2 diabetes. This medication is available in the form of tablets with three dosage options: 3 mg, 7 mg, and 14 mg. As per the manufacturer's recommendations, the initial prescribed dose for oral semaglutide is 3 mg taken once daily, followed by an increase to 7 mg once daily after a 30-day interval.^[37]

The key advantage of this semaglutide formulation is its oral delivery method, offering an alternative for individuals who may be facing difficulties in self-administering injectable medications designed to lower blood glucose.^[38]

9. Telemedicine

Telemedicine is a suitable approach for managing diabetes, as it enhances the monitoring of the condition and enables the storage and analysis of monitored data. Various aspects of diabetes management can be digitized, such as blood glucose levels, physical activity duration, step count, calorie intake, medication dosage, blood pressure, and weight. Software can identify patterns in this data, potentially leading to personalized treatment suggestions. Real-time decision-making and support for diabetes management can be facilitated by algorithms. Additionally, existing medical literature underscores the benefits of utilizing telemedicine in the management of diabetes.^[39]

Fig.7: Telemedicine treatment

• Sensor-Based Telemedicine

Telemedicine systems can be categorized into two primary groups: (1) systems that integrate automatically uploaded digital sensor data to generate descriptions, analyses, and treatment recommendations; and (2) systems that don't rely on sensors but instead facilitate communication between patients and healthcare professionals (HCPs) through deliberately uploaded messages or videos, with HCPs providing responses to patients.

When the initial form of telemedicine system (relying on digital sensors) is implemented through a wearable or mobile device, it is often referred to as mHealth. Mobile digital sensor telemedicine systems typically feature automatic data uploads, although there are a few mHealth systems that require patients to manually input digital data for cloud-based uploading. However, these mobile systems with manual data entry are seldom utilized, as most patients find the manual entry process laborious and tend to avoid using such systems.^[40]

- **Non-Sensor-Based TM**

The second category of telemedicine systems, which does not rely on sensors, is a more conventional form of telemedicine that predates the popularity of mobile sensors. Traditional non-sensor-based telemedicine primarily employs methods like phone calls, emails, and video communication initiated by the patient, and the majority of these communication methods necessitate deliberate (non-automatic) input.

Data generated by mHealth telemedicine systems (as well as stationary sensor-based systems) is usually digital and can be readily processed through automated software analysis. In contrast, data obtained from traditional non-sensor telemedicine systems is often analog and is generally unsuitable for automated software analysis.^{[41][42]}

10. Personalized medicine

The concept of personalized medicine is on the rise in disease treatment. It entails gathering specific information about an individual patient and tailoring the treatment to suit their unique characteristics. Personalized medicine involves identifying disease subtypes and biomarkers that can distinguish patients who are likely to benefit from a particular treatment from those who are unlikely to respond or may experience adverse effects.^[43]

Personalized Medicine for Diabetes (PMFD) can be defined as utilizing information about an individual's genetic profile that has diabetes to customize strategies for preventing, detecting, treating, or monitoring their condition. The practice of PMFD typically involves four key processes.^[44]

Firstly, it involves identifying specific genes and biomarkers associated with diabetes, as well as those linked to obesity.

Secondly, once these predictive factors for diabetes are recognized, it entails allocating resources towards the prevention or early detection of diabetes and/or obesity in individuals at a high risk, based on their genetic makeup.

The third step involves the selection of personalized treatment strategies for individuals who are affected. This selection process encompasses decisions regarding the choice of medication, the appropriate dosage of the medication, and the design of a suitable dietary plan. Additionally, it considers factors such as which medication is least likely to cause side effects or toxicity.

The fourth step centers on monitoring the response to preventive measures or therapy by measuring circulating biomarkers related to diabetes.^[45]

Fig.10: Personalized Medicine

Patients with diabetes, even those who share similar age, disease duration, body mass index, and HbA1c levels, do not consistently exhibit identical responses to a given treatment. Response variability may be attributed to genetic predispositions influencing the effectiveness of a drug. Physicians are required to individually evaluate each patient and make informed decisions about the most suitable treatment. Equipping physicians with personalized patient information, including genetic data, would enable the customization of treatments for each individual. This personalized approach holds the potential for achieving improved treatment outcomes while avoiding the unnecessary use of ineffective therapies.

CONCLUSION

Diabetes mellitus poses a significant health challenge in modern life. Lifestyle and daily circumstances play a pivotal involvement in the progression of such serious complications. The global prevalence of diabetes is on the rise, leading to an increase in diabetes-related complications among people of all ages, including younger adults, children, and adolescents. This trend is expected to substantially impact healthcare costs, particularly in managing heart-related issues and other long-term health problems associated with diabetes. Traditional medicines like tablets for diabetes were effective on using for a long term and they need to be administered on a regular basis. On the other hand, modern methods for treatment of diabetes are considered more effective since the approach and method used are more specific in identifying and managing the condition. In comparison with cost, the modern approaches may sound costly to some patients but they are more effective as compared to traditional medicines. It is essential to closely monitor patients with diabetes to ensure they attain and maintain both glycemic and non-glycemic treatment goals. To mitigate the growing burden of diabetes, preventive measures and significant lifestyle changes, including dietary improvements and increased physical activity, are imperative.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

Authors are also thankful to School of Pharmacy, Parul University for providing necessary facilities for the fulfillment of the current work.

REFERENCE

1. Roglic G. WHO Global report on diabetes: A summary. *Int. J. of Noncommunicable Diseases*. 2016 Apr 1;1(1):3-8.
2. Blair M. Diabetes mellitus review. *Urologic nursing*. 2016 Jan 1;36(1).
3. Deshmukh CD, Jain A, Nahata B. Diabetes mellitus: a review. *Int. J. Pure Appl. Biosci*. 2015;3(3):224-30.
4. Singh N, Kesharwani R, Tiwari AK, Patel DK. A review on diabetes mellitus. *The Pharma Innovation*. 2016 Jul 1;5(7, Part A):36.
5. Marín-Peñalver JJ, Martín-Timón I, Sevillano-Collantes C, del Cañizo-Gómez FJ. Update on the treatment of type 2 diabetes mellitus. *World J. of diabetes*. 2016 Sep 9;7(17):354..
6. Lean ME. Management of obesity and overweight. *Medicine*. 2011 Jan 1;39(1):32-8.
7. Garber AJ, Abrahamson MJ, Barzilay JI, Blonde L, Bloomgarden ZT, Bush MA, Dagogo-Jack S, DeFronzo RA, Einhorn D, Fonseca VA, Garber JR. Consensus statement by the American Association of Clinical Endocrinologists and American College of Endocrinology on the comprehensive type 2 diabetes management algorithm—2016 executive summary. *Endocrine Practice*. 2016 Jan 1;22(1):84-113.
8. Kaul K, Tarr JM, Ahmad SI, Kohner EM, Chibber R. Introduction to diabetes mellitus. *Diabetes: an old disease, a new insight*. 2013:1-1.
9. Mayfield J. Diagnosis and classification of diabetes mellitus: new criteria. *American family physician*. 1998 Oct 15;58(6):1355-1362.
10. American Diabetes Association. 2. Classification and diagnosis of diabetes: standards of medical care in diabetes—2021. *Diabetes care*. 2021 Jan 1;44(Supplement_1):S15-33.
11. Maffei C, Pinelli L, Brambilla P, Banzato C, Valzoler L, Ulmi D, Di Candia S, Cammarata B, Morandi A. Fasting plasma glucose (FPG) and the risk of impaired glucose tolerance in obese children and adolescents. *Obesity*. 2010 Jul;18(7):1437-1442.
12. National Diabetes Data Group. Classification and diagnosis of diabetes mellitus and other categories of glucose intolerance. *Diabetes*. 1979 Dec 1;28(12):1039-1057.
13. Zarkogianni K, Litsa E, Mitsis K, Wu PY, Kaddi CD, Cheng CW, Wang MD, Nikita KS. A review of emerging technologies for the management of diabetes mellitus. *IEEE Transactions on Biomedical Engineering*. 2015 Aug 19;62(12):2735-2749.
14. Sena CM, Bento CF, Pereira P, Marques F, Seica R. Diabetes mellitus: new challenges and innovative therapies. *New Strategies to Advance Pre/Diabetes Care: Integrative Approach by PPPM*. 2013:29-87.
15. Bequette BW. Challenges and recent progress in the development of a closed-loop artificial pancreas. *Annual reviews in control*. 2012 Dec 1;36(2):255-266.
16. Haidar A. The artificial pancreas: How closed-loop control is revolutionizing diabetes. *IEEE Control Systems Magazine*. 2016 Sep 15;36(5):28-47.

17. Dermawan D, Purbayanto MA. An overview of advancements in closed-loop artificial pancreas system. *Heliyon*. 2022 Nov 14;14:1-3.
18. Kovatchev B. Automated closed-loop control of diabetes: the artificial pancreas. *Bioelectronic Medicine*. 2018 Nov 7;4(1):14.
19. Matsumoto S. Islet cell transplantation for Type 1 diabetes. *J. of diabetes*. 2010 Mar;2(1):16-22.
20. Ichii H, Ricordi C. Current status of islet cell transplantation. *J. of hepato-biliary-pancreatic surgery*. 2009 Mar;16:101-12.
21. White SA, James RF, Swift SM, Kimber RM, Nicholson ML. Human islet cell transplantation—future prospects. *Diabetic medicine*. 2001 Feb;18(2):78-103.
22. Hussain MA, Theise ND. Stem-cell therapy for diabetes mellitus. *The Lancet*. 2004 Jul 10;364(9429):203-205.
23. Meier JJ, Bhushan A, Butler PC. The potential for stem cell therapy in diabetes. *Pediatric research*. 2006 Apr;59(4):65-73.
24. Xi Y, Bu S. Stem cells therapy in diabetes mellitus. *J Stem Cell Res Ther*. 2014;4(199):2.
25. Evans M, Schumm-Draeger PM, Vora J, King AB. A review of modern insulin analogue pharmacokinetic and pharmacodynamic profiles in type 2 diabetes: improvements and limitations. *Diabetes, Obesity and Metabolism*. 2011 Aug;13(8):677-684.
26. Wang F, Carabino JM, Vergara CM. Insulin glargine: a systematic review of a long-acting insulin analogue. *Clinical therapeutics*. 2003 Jun 1;25(6):1541-1577.
27. Pickup JC, Renard E. Long-acting insulin analogs versus insulin pump therapy for the treatment of type 1 and type 2 diabetes. *Diabetes care*. 2008 Feb 1;31(Supplement_2):S140-5.
28. Rodbard D. Continuous glucose monitoring: a review of successes, challenges, and opportunities. *Diabetes technology & therapeutics*. 2016 Feb 1;18(S2):S2-3.
29. Klonoff DC, Ahn D, Drincic A. Continuous glucose monitoring: a review of the technology and clinical use. *Diabetes Research and Clinical Practice*. 2017 Nov 1;133:178-92.
30. Vashist SK. Continuous glucose monitoring systems: a review. *Diagnostics*. 2013 Oct 29;3(4):385-412.
31. Chellappan DK, Sivam NS, Teoh KX, Leong WP, Fui TZ, Chooi K, Khoo N, Yi FJ, Chellian J, Cheng LL, Dahiya R. Gene therapy and type 1 diabetes mellitus. *Biomedicine & Pharmacotherapy*. 2018 Dec 1;108:1188-1200.
32. Lilly MA, Davis MF, Fabie JE, Terhune EB, Gallicano GI. Current stem cell based therapies in diabetes. *American J. of stem cells*. 2016;5(3):87.
33. Nauck MA, Vilsbøll T, Gallwitz B, Garber A, Madsbad S. Incretin-based therapies: viewpoints on the way to consensus. *Diabetes care*. 2009 Nov;32(Suppl 2):S223.
34. Peters A. Incretin-based therapies: review of current clinical trial data. *The American J. of medicine*. 2010 Mar 1;123(3):S28-37.
35. Koliaki C, Doupis J. Incretin-based therapy: a powerful and promising weapon in the treatment of type 2 diabetes mellitus. *Diabetes Therapy*. 2011 May;2:101-121.
36. Avgerinos I, Michailidis T, Liakos A, Karagiannis T, Matthews DR, Tsapas A, Bekiari E. Oral semaglutide for type 2 diabetes: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *Diabetes, Obesity and Metabolism*. 2020 Mar;22(3):335-345.
37. Rasmussen MF. The development of oral semaglutide, an oral GLP-1 analog, for the treatment of type 2 diabetes. *Diabetology international*. 2020 Apr;11(2):76-86.
38. Anderson SL, Beutel TR, Trujillo JM. Oral semaglutide in type 2 diabetes. *Journal of Diabetes and its Complications*. 2020 Apr 1;34(4):107520.
39. Franc S, Daoudi A, Mounier S, Boucherie B, Dardari D, Laroye H, Neraud B, Requeda E, Canipel L, Charpentier G. Telemedicine and diabetes: achievements and prospects. *Diabetes & metabolism*. 2011 Dec 1;37(6):463-476.
40. Poonguzhali S, Chakravarthi R. A sensor based intelligent system for classification and assistance of diabetes patients in telemedicine technology. *J.of Intelligent & Fuzzy Systems*. 2021 Jan 1;40(4):6365-6374.
41. Shuwandy ML, Zaidan BB, Zaidan AA, Albahri AS. Sensor-based mHealth authentication for real-time remote healthcare monitoring system: A multilayer systematic review. *J. of medical systems*. 2019 Feb;43:1-30.

42. Meersman D, Hadzic F, Hughes J, Razo-Zapata I, De Leenheer P. Health service discovery and composition in ambient assisted living: the australian type 2 diabetes case study. In 2013 46th Hawaii International Conference on System Sciences 2013 Jan 7 (pp. 1337-1346).
43. Kleinberger JW, Pollin TI. Personalized medicine in diabetes mellitus: current opportunities and future prospects. *Annals of the New York Academy of Sciences*. 2015 Jun;1346(1):45-56.
44. Cataldi S, Costa V, Ciccodicola A, Aprile M. PPAR γ and diabetes: beyond the genome and towards personalized medicine. *Current Diabetes Reports*. 2021 Jun;21:1-5.
45. Mohan V, Das AK, Mukherjee JJ, Seshadri K, Sujeet J, Sanjay K. From Individualized to personalized medicine in diabetes: an expert overview. *J. of the Association of the Physicians of India*. 2019:78.